

Job Satisfaction and Employee Turnover

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Abstract

This study is all about the major aspects of job satisfaction. Every human being has some basic needs in his life that he has to fulfill. If a job is unable to make him fulfill those needs, he or she won't be able to keep that job which will be non-satisfaction from the job. On the other hand, if a person gets the desired environment in a work place and also the job fulfills all his basic needs, the employee will show more retention, more dedication and more commitment while working in that organization. For effective job satisfaction it is necessary for the executives of can organization to fulfill the basic needs of their employees so that they may happily give their best to the business and contribute to the prosperity and growth of that organization. The staff should be given good salaries so that they may easily meet their daily expenses. In this study all these factors of job satisfaction has been analyzed and presented.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Basic need, Environment, Good salaries.

Introduction

Job satisfaction is basically an emotional satisfaction from an environment where a person works for fulfilling his financial needs. There are different factors that determine the satisfaction of employees from a particular person. A job may effectively satisfy an employee, but the same job may not satisfy the other employees. All these things are mostly dependent upon the type of personalities that the individual employees are having. For example, those employees who are more disciplined will find it easier to meet strict deadlines and deliver the best productivity (Taylor, 2000). On the other hand, those employees who have some sort of family issues or any other problems in their life, they won't be able to effectively manage at the tough jobs. So the key point is that job satisfaction mostly varies from person to person. There is no specific definition of job satisfaction. I.e. a satisfied software engineer will look different than the person who does job in military (Istyarini, 2019).

Work Environment

It is the overall system that exists inside a workspace. An effective work environment is the one in which the employees can perform at the level of their highest productivity and thus may bring about good results for the organization. The term "work environment" explains all the factors that are present in a particular system and have some impact on the working or performance of that system or an organization. The work environment includes the working hours too. A person may be working nine to five while there are some jobs in which the employees are given their due payments according to the time they give to the organization (Todd & Binns, 2011). Similarly, the culture of a company also comes in the work environment. There are some companies in which the employees have to dress strictly according to the stated rules and have to follow proper protocol and everything. While on the other hand, some organizations do not care for these things and their primary goal is to provide the best product or service to the customer and that's it (Luzio-Lockett, 1995).

Impact of Work Environment on Business Objectives

The work environment has the greatest impact on the objectives of business. Here are some of the major parameters explained in this regard.

1. Strict Environment

Such kind of work environment can be beneficial for some organization but for some organization it may not be an effective system. This completely depends upon the type of organization. For example a company who deals in medicine production should be having a strict environment in their core areas where the medicines are manufactured. This is due to the fact that medicines are very critical and they should be manufactured in the best standard as it is related to the health of the patients (Dwiedienawati, 2020).

There are certain types of organization where there is no need to run the system with great strictness. For example in local businesses, the employees can work smoothly along with the executives without making any tension (Mak & Sockel, 2001).

2. Friendly Work Environment

This is another type of work environment in which the employees generally manage their duties along with the directors and a kind of friendly relationships between the directors and the employees. Such type of work environment is also better to run everything smoothly and effectively. These types of environments generally exist in those organizations who do not primarily aims at winning the competition in the market and just focus on staying at least at the surface so that they may perform their business (Kelly, 1970).

3. Authoritative Environment

In this type of work environment, the managers generally command their task to the employees of lower positions. Everything and every process in such organizations is carried out in a rigid and strict manner. This type of environment is a formal one and the employees have to remain formal during their entire stay at the organization. Such kinds of system are generally regarded to be the best in terms of productivity as the employees are more committed to being formal and focusing on the results (Luzio-Lockett, 1995).

4. Compensation and Growth

Compensation and growth refers to the pay and benefits that the employees are given during their overall stay at the organization. It depends upon the position of an employee and as well as on the type of organization that the employee is working in. For example, a person working an a military department may need more security and protection as compared to the other one working in the civil department. This additional benefit provided to the military person is due to the nature of job that he is doing (Tsvetochkina & Baryshev, 2015).

The same concept applies to the other organizations too. A person who serves on managerial positions in a company is usually provided house rent or car facilities etc. This is generally done for creating an ease for that employee so that he may effectively work for the betterment of that organization. The best organization is the one that make the employees learn so that they may also grow as the organization grows. This concept of enabling the employees to get themselves more developed and advanced also make them think better for the organization and show and perform great sincerity towards that company (Todd & Binns,2011). If we discuss the salaries and basic pay, so that should always be given to the employees as according to the competitors of that organization (Dwiedienawati,2020).

Importance of Growth

Here are some of the major reasons that shows how much important it is to provide growth and compensation to the employees.

1. Increase Profitability

One of the greatest benefits of the compensation and growth to the employees is that it makes the employee feel more valued and thus he can give the best of himself to make the company more profitable. In such cases, the employees show great loyalty and commitments to the organization. This commitment of them to the company is greatly beneficial for the interests of the company. Every human have their basic needs in their life. Once their needs are fulfilled he can perform the best in his life and provide more benefit to the organization in which

he works. Therefore the business owner should provide all the basic needs to the employee so that he may find it easier to manage his life along with his professional life (Dwiedienawati, 2020).

2. Attraction of Talent

Organization that have the most talented employees are more successful in their lives as compared to those organizations whose employees are not that much experienced and effective. If the well talented people see an organization that they are providing nice salaries to its staff and taking care of the other needs of the staff, those persons will definitely attracted towards that organization. And thus due to the growth and compensation that the organization was providing, the company will get the best talent, which will ultimately contribute to the continuous growth and success of that organization (Manolopoulos, 2017).

3. Increase in Dedication

When the employees are motivated, they are more effective in their work and their productivity is always at the peak. The provision of nice compensation to employees and making rise in their wage packages make them feel motivated and thus working with more courage and zeal for the organization becomes easier for them (Tsvetochkina & Baryshev, 2015).

Work Life Balance

Work life balance is an important thing that needs to be considered in an organizational journey. Every employee is a human being too and thus he have the needs of his life that he has to fulfil. There are some jobs in which the employees have to take their work with their home too. For example, a person working in an organization and serving at a higher rank may have to do his tasks at home too for effective management of his time (Niessen et al., 2016). There are also certain jobs in which the employee has to keep himself ready for 24 hours. An example is that of a surgeon. If an emergency arises in the hospital and he is at home, he can never deny to go for attending that emergency. In such cases, he has to adopt a way of life so that he may find it no difficult to manage such like situations (Ziegler et al., 2016).

For the business firms and civil organizations, it is necessary to provide flexibility to the employees so that they may find it easier to contribute effectively and give the best to the company. It has been observed in many organizations that those companies who were not fulfilling the basic needs of the employees were left behind in the race of organizational success. This is due to the fact that these companies that when the employees are not given flexibility in time and other benefits they find it hard to manage their job when some emergency falls on them (Niessen et al.,2016).

Importance of Work Life Balance

Here are some of the main reasons why there should be work life balance in the life of an employee.

1. Money saving

One of the greatest things that a person can do in his life is to save money. That saved money can be used for various purposes. The best person in terms of finances is the one that knows how effectively money can be saved from daily expenses to be used to fulfill future needs. If a person is having poor work life balances. It always becomes difficult for him to manage his money. Such a person sometimes waste all his resources on useless wishes and sometimes get absorbed in his work to such an extent that he forget to take care of his daily life needs. If a person work with the greatest effectivity and become successful in managing his life with his work, in such a case he can best save his extra income from his salary that he can use for rainy days in his life (Mak & Sockel,2001).

2. Fulfillment of Needs

By effective work life balance the needs of the employees are effectively fulfilled and thus he can manage his life activities along with his job. Employees are never mechanical robots. They are humans and they do have problems in their personnel lives. Similarly, they have their needs that they have to fulfil in order to live in this world. The business owners should always give the opportunities to the employees to maintain their work life balance. If they are given this ease they would be able to work even better for the organization (Ngatat, 2012).

3. Skills Development

It is difficult for an employee to learn new skills of pursue higher education if he doesn't even get the time to manage all these things due to his work load. If a person is given enough time to manage his other activities like learning new skills or practicing the existent skills, he would become a better person in life and he may also work in a better way for the organization in which he works (Manolopolous, 2007).

Therefore, the business owner should give enough time to the employees to manage their other activities along with their work such as getting higher education or learning new skills. This will be highly beneficial for the future life of the employee and as well as for the organization (Tsvetochkina & Barsyshev, 2015).

Team work

One of the most effective factor that contributes to the betterment of organization and can help a company achieve its objectives is the team work. Team work enables the organization to use a great number of competent brains for the achievement of the collective organizational goals. A single brilliant mind can never be effective in deriving as much effective benefits as many minds can have. Therefore it is always better to work in teams as compared to working alone for creating an effective strategy and giving the best to the organization (Kumar, 2019).

It is of no use if a manager throws a group of employees into a room and asks them to develop a marketing strategy, if the employees are not experienced or doesn't possess the courage to solve an issue. All team management should be done as according to the needs of an organization and the skills and competency of level of the employees should also be assessed before giving them a job or assigning them a task (Mak&Socel, 2001).

Importance of Team Work

Here are some of the main things that show the importance of team work.

1. Support

When the employees work with each other and collaborate with each other, they always find out the best solution to their problems and through their support to each other, they manage everything with the greatest effectivity. Support from the other team mates also helps in building up nice and trust worthy relationships between them therefore it becomes easier for the employees to meet their deadlines on time and stay productive during their overall work at the company (Mak & Socel, 2001).

2. Communication

Communication is the most important thing in team work. Through effective communication employees share their ideas with each other and find out the best solution to their problems that arises during their stay at the organization. Communication is an effective tool that relaxes our mind and makes us mentally healthy and active. This highly contributes to the building up of positive energies between the employees and thus they become stronger and effective in their work. Team work also enables the employees to develop good connections between them and share their sincere thoughts with each other for the achievement of their objectives (Todd & Binns, 2011).

3. Effective Solution of Problems

One of the greatest benefits of team work is the solution of problems. Through team work problems are effectively solved and it becomes easier for the employees to work on themselves and find out the ways and methods to solve the great problems in the easiest possible manner and by the expenditure of the least resources. Team work boost up the ability of employees to solve their problems by sharing their problems with each other that they face during their working at the company (Ngatat, 2012).

Those employees that are good at managing and problem solving can cooperate effectively with other employees and make them more stronger and effective during their overall stay at the organization and thus the fresher's and non-experienced employees also learn the effective tactics to handle the projects and find out the best solution to the problems (Manolopoulos, 2017).

4. Loyalty

Loyalty can be called as one of the greatest character of morale. Those people who are loyal to their organizations and to their country always show greater honesty during their work. Therefore it is very necessary that their exist loyalty among the employees of an organizations. This loyalty among the team members to the organization greatly help that organization to manage their needs and they get some sincere and best employees who spend the resources of the company in the most wise and effective manner. Such kind of loyalty is always needed among the team members that keep the workers stay with each other and always work for the betterment of the company (Kumar, 2019).

Conflict Resolution in Team Work

One of the serious issues that generally arise during team work are the conflicts. These conflicts are creates due to several reasons in an organization. These conflicts require complete resolution in the best and most effective way. The team members need to find out the issues and figure out the most suitable solution for it. In such cases, conflicts can be resolved in the most effective way (Figuroa, 2016).

When working in teams it is obvious that the views and opinions of some people may not match with each other's. In such cases, when their opinions do not match, sometimes conflicts arises that can result in serious issue within an organization if not handled with the greatest effectivity. It is the prime responsibility of the executives or the directors to resolve the conflicts that arises during their work at the organization among the employees. The directors should be assisted by the team members to resolve all the problems and make the process flow on the track in the best possible way (Monolopoulos, 2017).

Motivation

Without motivation running a business is like running behind something that doesn't even exist. Employee motivation is the key thing required for the success of a company. When the employees are motivated and they are having the zeal and courage to work for the betterment of the company. They can be the best employees and they derive those benefits for the company that is sometimes beyond the expectations (Kumar, 2019).

Humans are the stores of emotions. Humans are highly controlled by the emotions. A leader who gets fail in managing the emotions of his employees can never make them work with such productivity and courage. The best and the ideal leader or executive is the one who provide goals to his employees, who incorporate the emotions in his employees to work with more courage and power (Sullivan, 1989).

Motivation brings about commitment to the job. The more the employees are motivated, the more they can perform effectively and productively. On the other hand, if the employees don't possess any motivation, they may not work with great effectivity and thus the success rate of the company will also be reduced. When the employees aren't motivated, they are not driven by the goals of the company and they only focus on getting their earnings and salaries which is their primary job. This not only reduces the productivity of that employee but also effect the productivity of the other employees working in that organization and hence the entire company run at a slow pace (Mak&Socel, 2001).

Key Importance of Motivation

The following are some of the main things that explain why motivation and staying motivated is important for the growth and success of a company.

1. Innovation

If a manager or executives wants to bring about some innovation in his company, he must take care of the motivations of his employees. The more the employees are courageous and motivated, the more they will be able to bring innovation and betterment in the working process of the company and thus the company will be able to manufacture or deliver the best product to the customers (Niessen et al., 2016).

2. Lower Absentees

If the workers of a company are motivated and effective in building out strategies, they do lower absentees from their work. When their motivation is high, they will even make themselves ready to do their tasks at home

too, so that they may not miss any minute and could work with the highest working productivity and bring the best output. Those employees that are acknowledged can work in the best way to make themselves better and more useful for the company (Kumar,2019).

3. Staff Retention

When the employees of an organization are motivated they are least likely to leave that company and work with the greatest productivity. Staff retention is the most essential thing for the success of a company. The organization in which the staff keeps on changing continuously can never get much successful during its overall journey. Therefore, it is necessary for the executives of a company to keep the employees motivated by providing them packages and benefits in different ways (Offor, 2018).

Steps to Keep the Employees Motivated

Here are some of the major steps to keep the employees motivated during their stay at the organization.

1. Arrange Meetings

Regular team and town hall meetings will keep your staff informed about new construction, goals, and targets; nevertheless, don't overburden your personnel with meeting requests! Employee motivation requires constant communication via a variety of methods. If face-to-face meetings are difficult to organize, use alternative channels to communicate what's going on, such as your intranet or internal magazine. People who aren't kept informed about what's going on will find it difficult to fully engage in the workplace; it's easy to feel undervalued if you're not told what's going on. It's difficult to stay on track if you don't know what you're aiming for (Sullivan,1989).

2. Train Them

If just one of your employees is stuck on a problem, enlist the support of the rest of the team to help them solve it. Spend an hour brainstorming idea - multiple fresh sets of eyes may help you come up with new ideas or strategies to put previously disregarded thoughts into action. If employees feel they can't go to other people for help because they're afraid of looking bad - or if their appeals for help fall on deaf ears - it's a sign of a more negative workplace culture. Collaboration and teamwork are crucial for a positive company culture (Todd & Binns, 2011).

3. Give them Goals

The most important lesson I've learnt in managing businesses over the last few years is to always define goals and objectives first. But how does this encourage employees to work harder? Employees' day-to-day roles take on new meaning when they set goals. According to research, employees who participate in a goal-setting journey are 3.6 times more likely to be engaged and motivated at work than those who do not. Recognize the function each individual is to perform in order to integrate the business goals with the employee objectives. According to surveys, 55% of employees are more motivated if they believe they are doing important work (Sullivan,1989).

4. Provide Support to Them

Top-level management must take measures to keep people motivated. Approach your teammates and assure them that you will be there for them whenever they require assistance. Encourage open lines of communication from the ground up and pay attention to what staff has to say. That way, you'll be able to grasp their frustrations and expectations, allowing you to establish a work climate that encourages productivity and boosts employee morale (Dwiedienawati, 2020). As a leader, you must have faith in your employees' abilities. This is because if you begin to believe in them, you will notice a rise in their confidence, productivity, and commitment. Supportive executives are good role models and work closely with their people.

5. Develop Positive Environment

The majority of employed people spend more than half of their day at work. This means that not only is a well-presented and well-maintained workplace important for their physical well-being, but it is also important for their mental health and productivity. Employees should be able to feel more at ease while also increasing their productivity in a pleasant working environment. This type of environment also creates a positive tone for the rest of the day, keeping your employees motivated. You may listen to your staff and involve them in the creative process, making them feel like they are a part of the organization. As a general rule, make sure the

office has sufficient illumination, ideally natural light. The interior must be kept clean at all times to ensure the highest level of hygiene (Tsvetochkina & Baryshev, 2015).

6. Reward the Employees

Employees who are motivated are more likely to perform better. When employees exceed expectations, it sometimes takes more than a pat on the back. Giving modest incentives to push people to become overachievers is the easiest approach to go around it. Top management might create a rewards program that honors employees when they reach particular workplace milestones (Wnuk, 2017). Employees should be rewarded and recognized on a regular basis to remind them that they are valued. You can choose appropriate gifts for employees that act as a reminder of your appreciation. You can inspire an employee even more by recognizing their successes outside of work, in addition to what they have done at work (Jinkins & Morin, 2018).

Social Interaction

Social interaction is another necessary factor of job satisfaction. It has been showed by various researches that relationships between the employees in organizations are very much important. No one can work alone without being good and professional relations with other employees. Employees spend majority of their time in their offices and work for earning their livelihood. Therefore, it is necessary for them to create and maintain good relations with other employees. In fact it is a need of them to being in a good relationship to the other employees around them and works collectively to achieve the collective goals of an organization. These relationships affect the level of their stress too. Those employees who are in good professional relationships with the other colleagues are more likely to produce the best productivity and results (Bipp,2016).

Key Importance of Social Interaction

The following are some of the main reasons why it is necessary to have social interaction in a workspace.

1. Happiness

There are various researches that show that relationships have impacts on our lives and our perceptions. Good relationships and social interaction among the workers of an organization make the workers feel happy and joyous and thus they can work without any pressure. This easiness and support can reduce a lot of problems for the company and can make everything run smoothly and effectively (Todd & Binns, 2011).

2. Reduce Stress

There are also different researches that have proved how social connections and being socially connected to other people reduces stress in a person's life. Being alone always causes problems to a person and make him feel worthless or not effective enough to carry out a process, although he is effective. Stress is one of the major problems that need to be managed to perform better at jobs. Making good friendships with other employees and treating them cheerfully and professionally greatly reduces the overall work tension and employees can easily perform a process through collaborating with each other (Kumar,2019).

3. Increase in Loyalty

Loyalty and sincerity is extremely important factors of which the executives should take care. Making good friendships with other employees increases the mutual trust and sincerity among the individuals and makes them work with more effectivity. It has been found that those employees having good relations among each other are more dedicated and enthusiastic in their work as compared to the other employees who didn't have much close relations with the other employees (Ong & Jeyaraj, 2014).

Training and Development

Studies had shown that those organizations that focus on the growth of the employees too along with the growth of the company had always been ahead in the race of sales and businesses. Those companies went higher, their revenue got doubled and they got authority in their products, by making their workers more valuable. And they made it done by training them in various ways (Offor, 2018).

According to a research 93 % of the employees will stay for longer time when the company in which they are working, invest in their growth and improvement. It is also recognized as the best thing ethically to make the

employees more empowered and make them better for their futures too. The training of employees should be started from the top, training directors and managers, then going towards the sales person and the workers of other departments in that organization.

When this process is completed, a hierarchy of developed and well equipped employees will be developed and thus all of them would work collective to make the organization achieve its organizational goals (Figueroa, 2016).

Major Benefits

The following are some of the major benefits of training and developing of employees

1. Greater Achievements

Those organizations that train and develop their employees are the best achievers of their goals. Through positive work and collective wisdom of all the trained employees these firms create their destiny for themselves and achieve real successes in their lives. Training the employees is same as sharpening the tools for making the process faster and more effective and thus objectives can be achieved in an easy and most simplified way. Therefore, it is the best to arrange training sessions for the employees and spend some budget on their improvement and development. This will be even more beneficial for the company too (Nemeckova,2012).

2. Creation of Leaders

There is a wise saying, that a leader is not the one who create followers, in fact it is the one who create leaders. Through training and development, leadership qualities among the employees are enhanced and thus they become able to take initiatives in case of need. Effective leaders are the effective brains that can bring out productivity easily within a limited time frame. And that is only possible if the employees are enabled to make them more experienced (Alleyne,2016).

Similarly, there is a best step towards greater achievements and successes in the business sector and that is providing more benefits and salaries to those people who are more skilled. This will not only increase their overall motivation for the work but will also make the other people get encouraged and focus on their goals (Isaacs, 2016).

3. Empowerment of Employees

Training the employees is making them more empowered. This enables them to work with more courage and they start learning the key strategies upon which the organization operates. This step is always beneficial for the company because the employees learn the factors which can bring more sales and more business for an organization (Nemeckova,2012).If the employees are well trained, they will feel more confident and will have more autonomy and will be more effective and useful for the organization. This will enable them to make their own decisions and take initiatives where required (Dwiedienawati, 2020).

Steps to Train Effectively

Here are some of the major steps that can be used to train the employees effectively in an organization.

1. Communicate

Clearly communicate the employee's role within the company's purpose, relevance, and value. Frequently, a manager will rapidly go through an employee's responsibilities with him or her. Although the manager may believe that this is the most effective approach to cover the content, it is frequently more expensive in the long term (Todd & Binns, 2011).

Employees will learn in a variety of ways. They pick up information by listening, seeing, and/or doing. The most efficient way for a wise trainer to assure mastery is to skillfully integrate a number of communication channels. For example, while the employee is watching, the trainer may demonstrate the procedures and stages, explain how the jobs relate to one another and to specific business objectives, and then encourage the employee to try it out (Ravenswood & Harris,2016).

2. Sincere Feedback

Encourage employees to ask questions, provide comments, and practice more. A new employee with a different point of view may be able to suggest methods to improve your company's operations. Your curiosity in what they have to say will help them contribute more effectively to the team. Make time for the employee to

complete a satisfaction and effectiveness feedback form after the training session. The feedback you receive might be quite useful in helping you improve the training sessions and the designated trainer (Dang et al., 2005).

3. Arrange Regular Trainings Sessions

You should organize training sessions for your personnel on a regular basis. Training on a regular basis can aid in the maintenance of skills and knowledge. Regular sessions are also an excellent approach to teach advanced skills and keep personnel informed of any changes (Bipp, 2010).

Staff meetings might be held on a regular basis. You might all meet in a huge room at your company for a brown-bag lunch or you could all meet in a restaurant's private dining room.

An all-staff meeting, while desirable, might be disruptive to corporate operations or even impossible due to multiple employee shifts. Instead of gathering everyone at once, you may organize meetings by shift, department, or even send out instruction by email. Alternatively, you might publish a note with a training checklist for staff to complete during their next shift (O'Brien-Smith & Rigby, 2010).

4. Set Training Objectives

You must determine whether or not your training program is effective. Set goals and keep track of whether or not they're being met to accomplish this. Decide what you want your staff to learn first. You can choose between a simple and a difficult goal. For example, you might want to make it a goal for all employees to read the training instructions for a specific piece of equipment. Alternatively, you may set a target for employees to be able to use the equipment independently within two weeks of reading the instructions (Manolopoulos, 2017). Consider who you want to help you achieve your goals when you set them. You can define objectives for the entire firm, a department, or individual employees. Conducting performance evaluations can assist you in setting goals and tracking their progress (Nemeckova,2012).

5. Set Employee Expectations

Employees' ability to perform at full capacity is hampered by poor communication. Setting employee expectations and properly communicating them to the employee is one of the finest ways for training new employees. Setting expectations ensures that you and your team are on the same page. It also provides an opportunity for the employee to ask any clarifying questions. Immediate open communication not only informs employees on expectations and operating procedures, but it also sets the tone for future learning and interactions in the workplace (Dechawatanapaisal, 2018).

Job security

One of the key factors of job satisfaction is job security. If a person is sure that the job he is doing is enough to fulfill his basic life needs, he feels secure about that job. Making an employee feel secure about his job is very essential in the overall process of working. This security make an employee work with complete dedication and provide the best part of himself and time to the company (Nemeckova,2012).

Every human has his basic needs whose fulfillment is extremely important. If a job is unable to fulfill all the basic needs of a person, then he will definitely try some other options and his talent may be used in the organizations of the competitors too. So it is very important for the employer to take care of these things and provide a job security to the workers so that they may never feel week during their work and may continue to actively take part in the processes of the company. The organizations should provide enough salary to the employees which are according to the work that is taken from him. All his basic needs should be fulfilled so that it is easier for him to work with complete dedication for the company (Scroggins, 2007).

Importance of Job Security

Job security ensures that a person will be able to manage his family life with his job. Without security of a job an employee can never show higher productivity. The basic needs of a person are the primary ones whose fulfillment is extremely important. An employee will always feel incomplete if his basic needs are left un fulfilled. This is where the security of jobs lies. A job will be more secure if it can fulfill all the needs of an employee (Niessen et al., 2016).

Those employees that are provided the security of their jobs can work for long term too for an organization. Those employees who have always the fear in their hearts to lose the job are always unable to take the risk of working for long term in a company. Similarly, it is also essential that the atmosphere of an organization is relaxed and organized and through job security, it is relaxed and employees can work by fulfilling their duties honestly and effectively. Employees engagement is also ensured by the job security. Doing a secure job can make the employees feel more engaged and thus they are able to achieve more. Job security multiplies the potentials of employees exponentially and thus they can easily derive the greatest benefits from the least resources. Similarly, recruiting may be costly for most of the companies. So job security can decrease the employee turnover and employees are better retained at the company in this way (Němečková, 2012). One of the best things about the job security is that it improves the image of that organization. Most of the clients would love to work with those companies who treat their employees in the best way and provide them the ease to do the work (Sullivan, 1989).

Conclusion

Job satisfaction is an entire procedure that focuses on fulfilling of all the factors that keeps an employee satisfied during his stay at the company. When the employee is given all the basic needs along with handsome income packages, he can deliver the best work and always shows more enthusiasm and energy to work for the organization. On the other hand, if the basic needs of the employees are left unfilled by a job, the employee won't be able to keep that job or work with honesty and dedication. There are hundreds of organizations operating in the world that focus on the retention of employees by keeping them satisfied and happy. Their employee retention enable them to produce good work during their work journey and ultimately the best and most effective products are provided to the customers due to the consumption of good talent of employees. True loyalty comes when true attachment is made. The business owners should never forget that employees are more attached to the organizations that provide them the best benefits and relief in different ways. So they should always focus on keeping the best talent with them by providing ease to the employees in different ways.

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